

UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' LIFE SATISFACTION: A COMPARISON ACCORDING TO SPORTING CIRCUMSTANCES

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to investigate the life satisfaction level of university students according to their sporting circumstances. Answers to the following questions have been sought to reach the main purpose of this study: a) what are the life satisfaction levels of students sporting and not sporting? b) Is there a significant difference between sporting situations and various variables in university students? The research is quantitative and descriptive survey model. The target population of research is composed of the students studying in Siirt University in 2016. The way of taking sample has been tried because of reasons such as the difficulty, time and cost of reaching target population. The sample group of this study consists of 519 students selected through cluster sampling method. It is considered that the sample presents the target population with a deviation of 0,5 because of the presence of 10,040 students in Siirt University. 'Life satisfaction scale' developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen and Griffin (1985) and adapted to Turkish by Şimşek (2011) has been used as a data collection tool in the study. It has been found that the Turkish translation of the Cronbach alpha coefficient is .87 (Şimşek, 2011). The scale consists of 11 items and is the one factor. Likert type5s grading has been used in the scale. The independence variables of the scale have consisted of open-ended short answers; the answers have been categorized by descriptive analysis method and new independence variables have been composed. For example; the answers to the question in the form "*what do you feel when you do sport?*" have been categorized and independence variables have been composed. The difference tests (T-test and ANOVA) have been used to look at the significance difference between independence variables and life satisfaction levels in the analysis of data. The arithmetic

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average and standard deviation amounts have been taken as basis for revealing life level. At the result of the research, it has been found that generally, the life satisfaction levels of the students were high, the life satisfaction levels of student's sports were relatively higher than students not sporting and there wasn't significant difference among branches of those sporting. It is also the result of the research that life satisfaction levels of those stating the reason of sporting was "*he/she feels bad*" were relatively higher than those stating sport 'for hobby'.

Keywords: sport, life satisfaction, university students

1. Introduction

The concept of sport originated in French has been emerged as 'mental' and 'physical' pleasure. It's known that sport has the effects such as being healthy and feeling at peace in the life of individual (Demir ve Filiz, 2004; Arslan & Ceviz, 2007; Koçak & Özkan, 2010; Özyazıcıoğlu, Kılıç, Erdem, Yavuz & Afacan, 2011). There are two related dimension: physical activity and mental activity. Physical activity is explained as all bodily movements that require spending energy and emerge from contraction of the skeleton muscles. Physical activity is the whole planned and continuous activities aimed at developing some elements of physical fitness (Karacabey 2009; Er 2016). It has been shown that nowadays many factors affect human health such as technological progress, working life, stress, unhealthy nutrition in spite of that physical activity doing regularly increases lifetime and life quality (Can, Arslan & Ersöz, 2014). The view that physical activity is necessary for organism has gained importance especially in terms of continuing life in healthy and quality way (Güçlü, 2008; Er, 2016). Cindaş (2011) has attracted notice that doing exercise is important for protecting health and the change of lifestyle, exercises decrease depression, stress and pains caused by muscles and skeleton, implicitly satisfaction that human will gain from life. The effect of physical activity and sport is great in curing the body and mental health of human and in feeling himself/herself safe (Bilge, 2000; Er, 2016). Hypertension in medium-level and blood pressure are lowered by aerobic activities and it is supplied more blood to the whole of the heart by these exercises (Pehlivan 2000; Er, 2016). These elements are maintained at the optimal level with regular exercises (Demir & Filiz 2004; Serin, 2016). Thus, life satisfaction is expected to increase with the protection of body health.

The concept of life satisfaction includes the person's general attitude towards life and emotional reactions about off - work life. The concept of life satisfaction related to many factors such as living well, being happy and high motivation has been the center of interest for psychosocial domains over the years (Acar Arasan, 2010; Sarıdemir,

2015). Therefore, it is thought that sport will provide positive contributions to life satisfaction. It is supposed that the life satisfaction levels of individuals sporting will be relatively higher than those not sporting. Participation in physical activity has positive effects on the individual in terms of living healthy and strengthening social relations. People try to fulfill the requirements of their living conditions (Er, 2016; Akça, 2012).

It is possible to get rid of the stress of the daily life and relax in terms of psychosocial by doing physical activity. The strengthening of mental health with physical practices is also topic (Can, Arslan & Ersöz, 2014). Providing participation in the mid and high level of physical activity is among important findings to increase life quality (Genç et al., 2011). The life satisfaction of individual is related to lots of factors. It has seen that life satisfaction is related to marital satisfaction, self-care ability, sport-specific satisfaction in the research conducted (Kara et al., 2014). Nevertheless, it is difficult to say that the desired awareness about sports and physical activities is provided in our country. In the research *"The research of relationship between physical activity level and socioeconomic level in adults"*, Deniz (2011) has observed that the level of physical activities of male is inactive and females are minimal active. Hence, it will be insufficient to say that it is understood adequately although it is shown that physical activity and life satisfaction of sport have effects on many factors. In this research, it is required to approach the subject from a different view by comparing the students sporting and not sporting and variables relating to sporting circumstances.

In this research, it has been aimed to compare the life satisfaction of university students sporting and not sporting and to examine the variables showing significant difference in life satisfaction. Answers to the following questions have been sought in order to reach the main purpose of the research:

- a) What are the life satisfaction levels of sporting and not sporting students?
- b) Is there a significant difference sporting circumstances among sex, age, branch of sports, the reason of sporting and the feeling after sport?

2. Method

The research is a quantitative and descriptive survey model. Survey researches are that the opinions of the participants about a topic or an event, and properties such as interest, skill, ability and attitude are identified; they are being the concerns of generalization (Büyükoztürk et al., 2009, 226).

2.1 Population Sample

The target population of research is composed of the students studying in Siirt University in 2016. The way of taking sample has been tried because of reasons such as the difficulty, time and cost of reaching target population. The sample group of this study consists of 519 students selected through cluster sampling method. It is considered that the sample presented the target population with a deviation of 0,5 because of the presence of 10,040 students in Siirt University. The personal information of the participants in the research is as the following table:

Table 1: The personal information of the participants in the research

Sex			Sporting Circumstance		
Subassemblies	f	%	Subassemblies	f	%
Male	281	54,1	Yes	311	59,9
Female	238	45,9	No	208	40,1
Age			The reason of sporting		
18-25	474	91,3	Because of problems	208	40,1
26-35	42	8,1	Feel well	179	34,5
36 +	3	,6	Hobby	132	25,4
Total			Do you have the branch of sport?		
Total	519	100,0	Yes	167	32,2
			No	352	67,8

2.2 Data collection tool

'Life satisfaction scale' developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen and Griffin (1985) and adapted to Turkish by Şimşek (2011) has been used as a data collection tool in the study. It has been found that the Cronbach alpha coefficient of the Turkish translations is 87 (Şimşek, 2011). The scale consists of 11 items and is the one factor. Likert type 5s grading has been used in the scale.

2.3 The analysis of data

The Independence variables of the scale have consisted of open-ended short answers, the answers have been categorized by descriptive analysis method and new independence variables have been composed. For example; the answers to the question in the form "What do you feel when you do sports?" have been categorized and independence variables have been composed. The difference tests (t-test and ANOVA) have been used to look at the significant difference between independence variables and life satisfaction level in the analysis of data. The arithmetic average and standard deviation amounts have been taken as basis for revealing life level.

3. Results

In this section, the differences between the life satisfaction level of the students taking place in the scope of sub-goal in the research and independent variables have been mentioned. Tables have been examined and commented.

Table 2: The life satisfaction levels of students sporting and not sporting

Sporting	N	X	Ss	Level
The sporting ones	311	3,83	,69	Very high
The non-sporting ones	208	3,56	,59	High

It has been seen that the life satisfaction levels of those sporting are very high ($X= 3,83$) and the life satisfaction levels of those not sporting are high ($X= 3,56$) when considering arithmetic average according to circumstances whether or not the students in the research sport. It can be said that in both cases the life satisfaction levels of university students in the research are over medium level.

Table 3: T- test results to the branch, feeling after sport,sex, sporting circumstances

	Subassemblies	N	X	ss	t	sd	p
Branch	Yes	167	3,83	,72	2,498	517	0,13
	No	352	3,67	,63			
Feelings	Good	210	3,56	,59	-4,518	502	,000
	Tired	294	3,83	,70			
Sex	Male	281	3,71	,69	-,404	517	,686
	Female	238	3,73	,64			
Sport	Yes	311	3,83	,69	4,573	517	,000
	No	208	3,56	,59			

When it has been examined that whether or not there is a significant difference between life satisfaction and the variables of student's branch, feelings after sport, sex, sporting, while it has been found that there is a significant difference in the variables of sporting and feelings after sporting ($p<.05$), it has not been found that there is a significant difference in the variables of branch and sex ($p>.05$).

In the research, it is seen that students feeling tired after sports ($X=3,84$) have relatively higher life satisfaction than those feeling well ($X=3,56$). This is an indication that it is suitable for the purpose of activity performed. Nevertheless, it has been seen that people sporting have relatively higher life satisfaction than those not sporting

Table 4: The Results of ANOVA Related to the Difference between the University Students' Reasons of Sporting and Life Satisfaction

Variables	X	ss		Sum of squares	sd	Averages of squares	F	Sig.	The reason of difference
1.Problems	3,56	,59	In group	13,99	2	6,994			
2.Feeling well	3,94	,66	Inter group	218,152	516	,423	16,543	,000	1*2;
3.Hobby	3,68	,71		2*3					
Total	3,72	,66		232,140	518				

A significant difference has been seen when examined the results of ANOVA related to the difference between the university students' reasons of sporting and life satisfaction ($p < .05$). At the result of Schfee test about the reason of difference, it has been seen that those sporting because of problems are between those sporting for hobby and for feeling well.

When examined the arithmetic average of subassemblies, It has been seen that the highest life satisfaction is the group sporting for feeling well, the following one those sporting for hobby and the last one those sporting because of problems (health problems, lipoidosis, obesity etc.)

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In this research examined whether or not sporting circumstances become different on life satisfaction, it has been seen that the university students sporting have higher life satisfaction than those not sporting. It has been also seen that those feeling tired after sport have higher life satisfaction than those feeling well. This situation has been seen as an expected conclusion as a result of the activity performed. Tiredness as a result of training or physical activity is parameter supplying satisfaction expected from sport. Tekkanat (2008), in the research called as 'The life satisfaction and physical activity levels of students studying in teaching department, has used World Health Organization Quality of life brief (WHOQOLBREF) to measure their life satisfaction and International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) to measure the levels of physical activity. Tekkanat has found positive and significant relation between life quality in physical area and the level of physical activity in all students and made firm that the level of physical activity has deterministic effect on the life quality in physical area. Significant difference has not been seen between university students sporting and those not sporting in the sexes and in the life satisfaction. Analogously, Genç et al. (2011) have not found significant difference between the variable of sex and life quality in the

research related to 'Being searched the differences of physical activity and life quality between female and male young adults'. In this case, it can be said that sex doesn't cause a significant difference in life quality.

At the result of the research, it has been seen that the students sporting have relatively higher life satisfaction than those not sporting. Analogously, Teoman et al. (2003) have found that the experimental group of females participated in six-week exercise have higher physical fitness and life quality than control group in their research on postmenopausal women. This result supports the research findings. Never the less when examined the researches in different countries in parallel with our research, it has been found significant results in the research of Vuillemin et al. (2005) which made on 2333 males and 3321 females from young adults and searched the relation between the life quality and physical activity. As a result of the analysis of multiple variance it has been determined that physical activity is related to life quality. It has been seen that the life quality scores of those participating in activity recommended level are higher than those not participating.

Finally, it has been seen that students who need sporting because of problems (health problems, lipoidosis, obesity etc.) have the least life satisfaction when examined the difference between the reasons of sporting and life satisfaction in university students. In this case, it can be said that reconciliation with sport is more effective and important in terms of life satisfaction before falling into a negative situation.

5. Suggestions

It has been determined that university students sporting have relatively higher life satisfaction than those not sporting. It is suggested that all individuals in society can be raised awareness about this case, they need to encourage doing sports in parallel with emergence of healthy society, all kinds of sporty domain about training students and young individuals need to expand and strengthen the sporty culture.

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